

STRUGGLES OF GOLDEN AGE TEACHERS IN TECHNO-SAVVY EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to explore the experiences and struggles of golden-age teachers in techno-savvy education and narrate their coping mechanisms to address the challenges they experienced in Lambayong III District for the school year 2023-2024. It employed a phenomenological study using thematic analysis in processing the responses of the participants.

On the struggles faced by the golden-age teachers in a techno-savvy education in doing online reports, meetings, and seminars. The following themes were generated poor internet speed connection and lack of professional training.

On the struggles faced by the golden-age teachers in a techno-savvy education in the teaching and learning process, the themes generated were difficulty in using the new technology and proficiency with digital communication tools

Interestingly, their coping mechanisms in a techno-savvy education to cope with the demands of a fast-changing world the following themes were generated in professional development and life-work balance.

Keywords: *Struggles, Golden age, Techno-savvy Education*

INTRODUCTION

The educational system around the world is undergoing increasing pressure to use the new information and communication technology to acquaint students with the

knowledge and information, they require in this techno-savvy Era. To develop a knowledge society, it is essential to integrate ICT at all levels of the education system.

Globally, many schools have already replaced traditional classroom setups with innovative flexible learning strategies since these are found to improve students' learning outcomes (Kim, 2010).

E-content is a very powerful tool of education. It is the latest method of instruction that has attracted the attention of learners and teachers of all instruction systems. It is a valuable resource for the development of an information-rich society where everyone, irrespective of caste, religion, race, region, and gender bias is empowered to create, receive share, and utilize information and knowledge for their economic, social, cultural, and political upliftment and development.

Learners and teachers from various instructional systems are welcome. It is a great resource for the construction of information-rich environments. The technology-driven world has touched almost all the fields and all the aspects of life. There has been a technological transformation in the field of education as well. E-learning has become a crucial aspect of the educational system. It is gaining momentum day by day. In such a technology-driven scenario, it has become a challenge for teachers to accommodate e-learning in their teaching-learning processes.

The study of Singh 2016 in India, states that to keep up with the demands of information explosion, information and communication technology have become crucial issues of academia. It is high time to equip teachers with advanced ICT and train them to avail maximum benefit from it. ICT is an integral part of our day-to-day life but it is still in the process of getting a better place in schools as a generation of teachers is not well acquainted with it but they are willing to adapt it.

Schools have become the most vulnerable to safety and security. Health concerns of school personnel, students, parents, and other stakeholders are at stake; thus, temporary closure of schools was enforced to contain the spread of the virus and reduce infections (UNESCO, 2011).

Thus, this study was capsulized and It will emphasize the challenges faced by golden age teachers in Lambayong District III.

Research Questions

The study focuses on the struggles and coping mechanisms of golden-age teachers in techno-savvy education. Specifically, the study will be carried out with the following objectives:

1. What are the struggles faced by the golden-age teachers in a techno-savvy education in doing online reports, meetings, and seminars?
2. What are the struggles faced by the golden-age teachers in a techno-savvy education in the teaching and learning process?
3. What are the coping mechanisms of golden-age teachers in a techno-savvy education to cope with the demands of fast changing world?

METHODOLOGY

This investigation employed a phenomenological research design as it can study people's experiences, how people construct meaning in their lives, and commonalities that transverse individuals experiencing a specific phenomenon (Edmonds & Kennedy, 2017). Notably, this study utilized Transcendental phenomenology, which aimed to seek understanding in human experience, which is performed by laying aside prepossessed ideas in order to view the phenomena to be investigated through a new lens, allowing it to immerge, giving its distinct meaning and form (Moustakas, 2004).

The focus participants of this investigation are ten (10) teachers with the age range fifty and above regardless of the plantilla position, who were selected through purposive sampling. This phenomenological study selected seven (7) participants that fit the suggestion of Creswell (2014) as an ample number of participants to generate meaningful themes and valuable interpretations.

RESULTS

On the struggles faced by the golden-age teachers in a techno-savvy education in doing online reports, meetings, and seminars. The following themes were generated **poor internet speed connection and lack of professional training.**

On the struggles faced by the golden-age teachers in a techno-savvy education in the teaching and learning process, the themes generated were **difficulty in using the new technology and proficiency with digital communication tools**

Interestingly, their coping mechanisms in a techno-savvy education to cope with the demands of a fast-changing world the following themes were generated in **professional development and life-work balance.**

DISCUSSION

On the struggles faced by the golden-age teachers in a techno-savvy education in doing online reports, meetings, and seminars

The following themes were generated on the struggles faced by the golden-age teachers in a techno-savvy education in doing online reports, meetings, and seminars **a. poor internet speed connection**, and **b. lack of professional training**.

Poor internet speed connection is the first theme that was generated.

In this digital age, the Internet has become a powerful tool for connecting people, information, ideas, resources, and services. It has become a driving force of the economy and has provided employment, transformed industries, improved infrastructure, and provided efficient communication among enterprises and individuals across the globe. With a slow Internet connection, citizens are less likely to be motivated to participate in today's information society.

In some countries, the essential role of this tool is well understood, and the right to broadband Internet access as a means of communication is spoken of as a fundamental right.

In this theme the participants shared:

“The struggles faced in a techno-savvy education in doing online reports, meetings, and seminars are a poor internet speed connection, no internet connection sometimes unavailability of gadgets and computers.”
Participants 1, Grade VI teacher, female, 51 years old.

“Poor networks, log devices, and the system of technology that I use is affect my skills because no matter how good our skills when the gadgets are the problem we can't overcome it with our skills”. **Participant 4, Grade I teacher, female, 52 years old**

Another significant issue is poor internet connectivity resulting from limited bandwidth due to the absence of appropriate infrastructure to deliver quality mobile services in developing countries (Shrestha *et al.*, 2010). Austin and Bradley (2005) indicated that accessing and utilizing information and communication technology (ICT) is technically much easier when one has a broadband internet connection.

On the struggles faced by the golden-age teachers in a techno-savvy education in the teaching and learning process

The sudden transition of learning impels teachers to learn more about technology, how they can deliver their lessons, and how they can keep the students engaged despite distance learning. Throughout its course, teachers of all ages had different dilemmas, Perez et al (2022). In this abrupt change of classroom set-ups, the senior aged teachers are believed to have been the most affected.

The themes generated on the struggles faced by the golden-age teachers in a techno-savvy education in the teaching and learning process are **a. difficulty in using the new technology**, and **b. proficiency with digital communication tools**.

An evaluative study conducted by Octavia et al., (2021) infers the idea that proficiency in digital understanding and their insufficient cognition about technological abetment and its advancement is one of the challenges they faced in online class. The majority of the participants suggested that the provision of the additional ICT courses in the shape of educational summits, exclusive training courses, and directive courses will somehow relieve their difficulties.

Along with this context the participants of the study shared their view as;

“In my own experience if I have difficulty preparing my lesson using the new technology I ask my co-teacher to help to do so”. **Participants 1, Grade VI teacher, female, 51 years old**

“The problem is the materials specifically when able to teach and share the knowledge we learned but we are not capable prove it properly because of not enough materials”. **Participant 4, Grade I teacher, female, 52 years old**

On the coping mechanisms in a techno-savvy education to cope with the demands of fast changing world

The following formulated themes with this statement were **a. professional development** and **b. life work balance**.

Professional development is gaining new skills through continuing education and career training after entering the workforce. It can include taking classes or workshops, attending professional or industry conferences, or earning a certificate to expand your knowledge in your chosen field.

The following are the coping mechanisms golden aged teachers developed and they mentioned themselves.

“I am willing to learn by attending seminars and asking a help from a knowledgeable person”. **Participant 1, Grade Vi teacher, female, 51 years old**

“By attending trainings and seminars and asking for assistance from those who have the most knowledge in manipulating picture”. **Participant 3, Relieving teacher, female, 58 years old**

Professional development is important because it has the potential to open opportunities for career advancement, such as promotions. It can assist you in honing existing skills and in learning new ones.

Professional development among instructors is widely known for its importance as it serves as their ground in upgrading their abilities as an individual and as an instructor.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

Teachers struggle with the internet speed connection in school if there are training, meetings, and seminars to be attended virtually, lack of professional training on the use of some applications embedded in the technology was also their struggle.

Teachers have difficulty using the new technology in the teaching and learning process because they don't have proficiency with digital communication tools and applications.

But somehow golden-age teachers are eager to have professional development to cope with the demands of the fast-changing evolution of technology in the fast-changing world coupled with life-work balance as they face those challenges they had experienced in teaching and learning process and the demands of their duties and responsibilities as an agent of change and prime movers of the basic education in the department of education.

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented; The school may be included on their school operating budget to allocate budget for a more accurate speed internet connection. The school learning action cell focal person may craft a continuous learning development that may include the use of information and communication technology. That this study be replicated in wide scope to have a clearer picture of in-person classes quantitatively.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms the ethical standards.

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